

Prevalence of Osteoporosis in Liver Cirrhosis.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the prevalence of osteoporosis in liver cirrhosis.

Place and duration of study: This study was carried out in Liver clinic or Mayo Hospital Lahore in a duration of 6 months from December 2018 to May 2019.

Materials and Methods: 50 patients were selected for the study. Both males and females were included in this study on random basis. Only those patients were selected who were willing to take part in this study. 40 to 70 years was the mean age and in all the patients either Hepatitis B or C was the reason for cirrhosis of liver. In all the patients DEXA scan was obtained and if the T value was less than 2.5 it was considered osteoporosis. Informed consent was taken from all the patients or their relatives.

Results: Among the selected 50 patients, 36% were females and 64% were male patients. 47 years was the mean age of the patients. Osteoporosis was found in 14 (28%) of the patients. 10 (31.25%) males were affected and it was greater than the percentage of female patients. Higher incidence was seen in patients with increasing age. Incidence was not related to the time duration for which the patient had cirrhosis.

Conclusion: Osteoporosis in case of liver cirrhosis is very common and every 4th or 5th patients with cirrhosis develops osteoporosis. It is usually neglected and considered insignificant. The complications increase with the increase in age.

Keywords: Osteoporosis, Cirrhosis, DEXA scan.

Introduction: Fibrotic changes in the normal architecture of the liver is defined as cirrhosis which is reversible initially but becomes irreversible at later stage and ultimately results in liver failure. In different phases inflammation and regrowth occurs which leads to fibrosis. As these processes are irreversible which can result in serious health issues and lead to the death of patient. Prevalence in different areas of the world is different but in underdeveloped countries like

India, Bangladesh and Pakistan it is higher than other countries. Various complications like ascites, osteoporosis, encephalopathy, hepatorenal syndrome and esophageal varices can develop. Osteoporosis caused by cirrhotic liver has been ignored in past and treated as a minor complication but recently attention has been paid to it as a serious complication. Bone mineral density is decreased in osteoporosis. According to the studies done recently, it has been shown that there is higher frequency of demineralization of bones in patients with liver cirrhosis as compared to the people in which no cirrhosis is seen. Among one lac patient almost 20 to 420 patients are affected. Factors like age, smoking, female gender, decreased sunlight exposure, genetics and other factors like drinking habits and diabetes play a significant role in the development of osteoporosis. Variable cytokines and mediators like fibronectin and insulin like growth factors have significant impact on the development of diseases but the fact that liver cirrhosis is solely responsible for the development of osteoporosis is still debatable. For measuring bone density, DEXA scan is the most commonly used investigation. 26% incidence of osteoporosis was reported by Javed M et al in his study while Cijevski C et al reported 38% incidence.

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Discussion: Portal hypertension, cyanosis, ascites, esophageal webs, clubbing and various systemic problems can occur due to cirrhosis due to which mortality rate is increased. Cirrhosis can lead to multiple system failure due to which morbidity and mortality is increased. Rate of other related complications like decreased sunlight exposure and decreased oral intake is also increased that results in osteoporosis. In our study, 28% incidence rate of

osteoporosis associated with cirrhosis is seen which is close to other studies where 20-50% incidence rate is seen. The results usually vary because of the different indicators used for collecting data and the method used for measuring density of bone. Bone density is usually measured from bone where there is high pressure like vertebrae and heel. The use of same parameters by Javed M et al revealed the same results where he showed 26% incidence. With the increasing age, the incidence rate increased to 33.3%. The same correlation has been shown with age in previous studies. Increasing age is the greatest risk for developing osteoporosis.

Conclusion: Osteoporosis in case of liver cirrhosis is very common and every 4th or 5th patients with cirrhosis develops osteoporosis. It is usually neglected and considered insignificant. The complications increase with the increase in age.

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